

A FAUNAL STUDY ON PLANT BUGS (HEMIPTERA: HETEROPTERA: MIRIDAE) IN THE CENTRAL PART OF SOUTH KHORASAN PROVINCE, IRAN

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Abstract

This research was carried out in 2022 in the central part of South Khorasan province, Iran. Twenty-two species of plant bugs (Hemiptera: Miridae) belonging to 17 genera and 3 subfamilies, including Deraeocorinae (1 genus and 1 species), Mirinae (8 genera and 9 species) and Phylinae (8 genera and 12 species), were collected and identified from different host plants. In this report, three species including *Ectagela* sp., *Megacoelum brevirostre* and *Adelphocoris ticinensis* were reported from South Khorasan province for the first time. All specimens are preserved in the insect collection of the Natural History Museum of the University of Guilan.

KEY WORDS: Deraeocorinae, Mirinae, Phylinae, South Khorasan Province, Iran

Introduction

Miridae (Insecta: Heteroptera) is the largest family of Hemiptera, with more than 11,000 described species. It is subdivided into eight subfamilies, with almost 50 tribes (Cassis & Schuh, 2012; Menard *et al.*, 2013; Namyatova & Cassis, 2016). Miridae species demonstrate various food preferences and behaviors, including phytophagy, predatory, and omnivory (Cassis & Schuh, 2012).

Almost 600 species of Miridae classified into 140 genera and 7 subfamilies for Iranian fauna have been reported (Linnavuori & Hosseini, 1998, 1999, 2000; Linnavuori & Modarres, 1999; Hosseini & Linnavuori, 2000; Hosseini *et al.*, 2000; Magnien & Matocq, 2008; Linnavuori, 2006, 2007, 2009, 2010; Lashkari & Hosseini, 2012; Hosseini, 2013 a, b, c; 2014 a, b; Hosseini & Shamsi, 2014; Malvandi *et al.*, 2015; Hosseini, 2016, 2017; Mohammadi *et al.*, 2018 a, b; Zamani & Hosseini, 2018; Hosseini & Mohammadi, 2018, 2019^a,^b; Zamani & Hosseini, 2019, 2020, 2022).

Khorasan is a large province in eastern Iran that was recently divided into three different regions: North Khorasan province, Razavi Khorasan province, and South Khorasan province. Each of these regions has its own unique climate and weather conditions. South Khorasan province is located at 55.6 to 60.57 longitude and 30.31 to 35.10 latitude, and consists of highlands and plains. It has a hot and dry desert climate in the lowlands and a semi-arid climate in the highlands. Birjand is the capital city of South Khorasan province, with a minimum temperature of -22 and a maximum of 43. The vegetation of the province includes forests and dry, hilly steppes. The most abundant plant species in the forests include *Pistacia atlantica*, *Amygdalus scoparia*, *Amygdalus lycioides*, *Cercis* sp., *Ficus* sp., and *Prosopis cineraria*. Plants in the dry, hilly steppes include *Ferula assa-foetida*, *Achillea millefolium*, *Rheum* sp., and *Thymus* sp. (The General Bureau for Textbooks Printing and Distribution, 2023). A few studies have been conducted in Razavi and North Khorasan provinces (Linnavuori & Modarres, 1998, 1999; Modarres Awal, 1997a, b; Havaskary *et al.*, 2010; Malvandi *et al.*, 2015). Only one study has been done on the fauna of Heteroptera in South Khorasan province. Mohammadpour *et al.* (2017) identified 20 species and subspecies belonging to 15 genera of 7 families in the alfalfa fields of Ghaen, of which 8 species were Miridae. According to these records, no study has focused on the plant bug fauna in the center of South Khorasan province. Therefore, our study was an effort to fill this information gap.

Materials and Methods

Sampling was carried out in three counties of South Khorasan province, namely, Birjand, Khosf, and Arian Shahr, during spring and summer in 2022, using two different methods. These methods varied based on the habitat, vegetation cover, and species type. Mirid bugs were collected randomly from gardens and fields on different host plants using an insect net and sweeping the vegetation in different habitats or beating tree branches. A light trap was also used. The trap had a 100-watt lamp directly connected to the household electricity. The collected specimens were killed by ethyl acetate, transferred to the laboratory, mounted on triangular cards, and labeled.

For the study of genitalia, the pygophore was removed and softened in boiling water for a few minutes, and then male genitalia were dissected in a drop of glycerol. Photographs of specimens were taken using a Canon EOS 200D camera equipped with a Canon EF 100mm f/2.8 Macro USM macro lens attached to a 65 mm Meike macro extension tube. Partially focused images of specimens were combined in Helicon Focus software (ver. 6.7.1). Then, they were modified and formatted in Photoshop CS6. All specimens are preserved in the insect collection of the Natural History Museum of the University of Guilan.

Results

A list of species, including 22 species belonging to 17 genera and 3 subfamilies, is given below.

Subfamily Deraeocorinae Douglas & Scott, 1865

Tribe Deraeocorini Douglas & Scott, 1865

***Deraeocoris (Camptobrochis) punctulatus* (Fallén, 1807)**

Material examined: Iran, South Khorasan province: Piranj (33°03585'N, 59°29708'E. 1850m), 13.05.2022, 3 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂. Khorashad (32°75126' N, 59°40478'E. 1470m), 06.07.2022, 1 ♂. Afzalabad (33°13392'N, 59°16910'E. 1641m), 21.07.2022, 1 ♂.

This species was collected on *Brassica napus* (Fig. 1-C, D) by sweeping and light trap (Fig. 2-A).

Distribution in Iran: Alborz (Modarres Awal, 1997c; Linnavuori, 2007), Ardabil (Modarres Awal, 1996; Linnavuori, 2007; Havaskary *et al.*, 2012), East Azerbaijan (Hassazadeh *et al.*, 2009 a, b; Gharaat *et al.*, 2009; Ghahari *et al.*, 2011), Fars (Alemansoor & Ahmadi, 1993; Modarres Awal, 1997 c; Linnavuori, 2009; Zarei *et al.*, 2012), Golestan (Khormali, 2000; Ghahari & Ostovan, 2006), Guilan (Abd-Rabou & Ghahari, 2006; Linnavuori, 2007), Hamadan (Mirab-balou *et al.*, 2007, 2008), Ilam (Linnavuori, 2009), Isfahan (Modarres Awal, 1997 c; Linnavuori, 2009; Rakhshani *et al.*, 2010), Kerman (Wagner, 1961; Kiritshenko, 1966, with doubt), Kermanshah (Linnavuori, 2009), Khorasan (Reuter, 1904; Modarres Awal, 1997 b; Linnavuori & Modarres Awal, 1999; Havaskary *et al.*, 2010), Kordestan (Linnavuori, 2009; Ebrahimi *et al.*, 2012), Kuhgiluyeh & Boyerahmad (Linnavuori, 2009), Lorestan (Linnavuori, 2009), Markazi (Linnavuori, 2009; Arkani *et al.*, 2011), Mazandaran (Heiss & Linnavuori, 2002; Ghahari & Ostovan, 2006; Ghahari *et al.*, 2008 a, b, 2009), Qom (Wagner, 1961), Semnan (Jakovlev, 1877), Sistan & Baluchestan (Kiritshenko, 1966), Tehran (Lindberg, 1938; Linnavuori, 2007), West Azerbaijan (Gharaat *et al.*, 2009; Linnavuori, 2009), Yazd (Linnavuori, 2009), Zanjan (Linnavuori, 2007): cited references in Ghahari & Cherot (2014); South Khorasan (Mohammadpour *et al.*, 2017).

General distribution: Europe: Albania, Austria, Belgium, Byelorussia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, European Kazakhstan, European Turkey, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Liechtenstein, Lithuania, Moldavia, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Russia (Central, North and South European Territories), Serbia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine. Asia: Azerbaijan, Afghanistan, Armenia, Asian Kazakhstan, Asian Turkey, China (Northeastern, Northern, Northwestern, Southwestern Territories and Western Plateau), Cyprus, Georgia, Iran, Iraq, Kirgizia, Korea, Mongolia, Russia (East Siberia, Far East and West Siberia), Syria, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, Karakalpakstan (Sadullaevich & Mirganievna, 2022). Extralimital: North America (Alaska, Canada). (Aukema, 2023).

Subfamily Mirinae Hahn, 1833

Tribe Mirini Hahn, 1833

***Adelphocoris ticinensis* (Meyer-Dur, 1843)**

Material examined: Iran, South Khorasan province: Bandeomارشah (32°83051'N, 59°18209'E. 1743m), 08.05.2022, 1 ♂. Khorashad (32°75126' N, 59°40478' E. 1470m), 06.07.2022, 1 ♀.

This species was collected on *Achillea* sp. by sweeping and light trap (Figs. 1-G, H; 3-E, F).

Distribution in Iran: Guilan (Linnavuori, 2007; Hosseini, 2014), Mazandaran (Wagner, 1957; Linnavuori, 2007).

General distribution: Europe: Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bosnia, Hercegovina, Bulgaria, Byelorussia, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Kazakhstan, France, Great Britain, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Macedonia, Moldavia, Montenegro, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Russia (Central and South European Territory), Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine. Asia: Armenia, Asian Kazakhstan, Asian Turkey, Azerbaijan, Georgia, Iran (Aukema, 2023).

Figure 1. Habitats and plant associations: A, B – habitat of *Reuterista unicolor* and *Eurystylus bellevoeyi*; C, D – habitat of *Lygus gemellatus*; E, F – habitat of *Compsidolon nebulosum* and *Compsidolon elegantulum*.; G, H – habitat of *Adelphocoris ticinensis* and *Campylomma verbasci*.

***Creontiades pallidus* (Rambur, 1839)**

Material examined: Iran, South Khorasan province: Golefrize (32°68842'N, 59°16115'E. 1831m), 01.09.2022, 1 ♂.

This species was collected by light trap.

Distribution in Iran: Bushehr (Linnavuori, 2009), Fars (Linnavuori, 2009; Zarei *et al.*, 2012), Golestan (Karimian & Khormali, 2006; Linnavuori, 2007; Ghahari, 2013), Hormozgan (Linnavuori, 2004), Kerman (Wagner, 1958 as *C. p. virens*; Kiritshenko, 1966; Linnavuori, 2009; Shamsi *et al.*, 2014), Khorasan (Linnavuori & Modarres Awal, 1999; Hosseini *et al.*, 2006), Khuzestan (Linnavuori, 2009), Markazi (Linnavuori, 2009), Sistan & Baluchestan (Wagner, 1957 as *C. p. virens*; Kiritshenko, 1966), Tehran (Linnavuori, 2007), West Azerbaijan (Gharaat *et al.*, 2009), Zanjan (Linnavuori, 2007); cited references in Ghahari & Chérot (2014); Rafsanjan (Zeinadini *et al.*, 2015), Razavi Khorasan (Malvandi *et al.*, 2015), South Khorasan (Mohammadpour *et al.*, 2017).

General distribution: Europe: Crete, France, Greece, Italy, Malta, Sicily, Spain. North Africa: Algeria, Canary Islands, Egypt, Libya, Morocco, Madeira, Tunisia. Asia: Arab Emirates, Turkey, Cyprus, Iran, Iraq, Israel, Jordan, Saudi Arabia, Sinai, Yemen. Extralimital: tropical Africa, Brazil (introduced) (Aukema, 2023).

***Eurystylus bellevoeyi* (Reuter, 1879)**

Material examined: Iran, South Khorasan province: Rukaat (32°80758'N, 59°07374'E. 1690m), 28.03.2022, 1 ♀. Mazarerazg (32°80682'N, 59°26600'E. 1792m), 04.05.2022, 24.03.2022, 6 ♀♀. Afzalabad (33°13392'N, 59°16910'E. 1641m), 21.07.2022, 1 ♀.

This species was collected on *Triticum* sp. by sweeping and light trap (Fig. 2-B).

Distribution in Iran: Fars (Linnavuori, 2009; Zarei *et al.*, 2012), Golestan (Khormali, 2000 under the spelling *E. bellevoeyi* [sic]), Guilan (Linnavuori, 2007), Hormozgan (Linnavuori, 2004), Kerman (Wagner, 1958; Modarres Awal, 1997c; Linnavuori, 2009, Shamsi *et al.*, 2014), Khorasan (Wagner, 1957; Modarres Awal, 1997b; Linnavuori & Modarres Awal, 1999; Havaskary *et al.*, 2010), Khuzestan (Linnavuori, 2009), Kordestan (Ebrahimi *et al.*, 2012), Markazi (Arkani *et al.*, 2011), Sistan & Baluchestan (Wagner, 1957; Kiritshenko, 1966), Yazd (Linnavuori, 2009), Zanjan (Linnavuori, 2007); cited references in Ghahari & Chérot (2014); Rafsanjan (Zeinadini *et al.*, 2015), Razavi Khorasan (Malvandi *et al.*, 2015).

General distribution: Europe: France, Greece, Italy (Sicily, Pantelleria, Vulcano Island), Malta, Spain. North Africa: Canary Islands, Egypt, Libya, Morocco, Madeira, Tunisia. Asia: Afghanistan, Arab Emirates, Asian Turkey, Cyprus, Iran, Iraq, Israel, Jordan, Kuwait, Oman, Saudi Arabia, Sinai, Turkmenistan, Yemen. Extralimital: Oriental regions (India, Pakistan, Sri Lanka) and tropical Africa (Aukema, 2023).

***Lygus gemellatus* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835)**

Material examined: Iran, South Khorasan province: Mazarerazg (32°80682'N, 59°26600'E. 1792m), 24.03.2022, 1 ♀. Hossein Abad (32°8360'N, 59°1974966'E. 987m), 11.04.2022, 1 ♀. Khorashad (32°75126'N, 59°40478'E. 1470m), 06.07.2022, 1 ♀. Esfahrod (32°8054'N, 59°303285'E. 1000m), 29.03.2023, 1 ♀.

This species was collected on *Cynoglossum* sp. by sweeping (Fig. 1-D) and light trap (Fig. 2-A).

Distribution in Iran: Ardabil (Linnavuori, 2007; Havaskary *et al.*, 2012), East Azerbaijan (Sadaghian *et al.*, 2004; Nikdel *et al.*, 2011; Havaskary *et al.*, 2012), Fars (Miyamoto, 1963; Linnavuori, 2009; Zarei *et al.*, 2012

as subspecies *Lygus g. gemellatus*), Golestan (Heiss & Linnavuori, 2002; Khormali, 2000; Karimian & Khormali, 2006; Linnavuori, 2007), Guilan (Linnavuori, 2007), Hamadan (Khanjani & Kalafchi, 2000; Mirabalou *et al.*, 2007, 2008; Mirabalou & Radjabi, 2013), Isfahan (Hoberlandt, 1955; Yarmand *et al.*, 2004; Razmjoo *et al.*, 2011), Kerman (Linnavuori, 2009, Shamsi *et al.*, 2014), Khorasan (Reuter, 1904 under the name *L. pratensis* var. *gemellatus*; Modarres Awal, 1997b; Linnavuori & Modarres Awal, 1999; Heiss & Linnavuori, 2002; Havaskary *et al.*, 2010), Kordestan (Linnavuori, 2009; Ebrahimi *et al.*, 2012 under the spelling *Lygus gemellats* [sic]), Markazi (Linnavuori, 2009; Arkani *et al.*, 2011), Mazandaran (Linnavuori, 2007), Tehran (Kiritshenko, 1966; Linnavuori, 2007), Yazd (Linnavuori, 2009), Zanjan (Linnavuori, 2007): cited references in Ghahari & Chérot (2014); Razavi Khorasan (Malvandi *et al.*, 2015), South Khorasan (Mohammadpour *et al.*, 2017).

General distribution: Europe: Albania, Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bosnia, Hercegovina, Bulgaria, Byelorussia, Crete, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, European Kazakhstan, European Turkey, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Liechtenstein, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Moldavia, Montenegro, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia (Central, North and South European Territory), Serbia, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine. North Africa: Algeria, Madeira, Morocco, Tunisia. Asia: Azerbaijan, Afghanistan, Armenia, Asian Kazakhstan, Asian Turkey, China (Northern, Northwestern Territories and Western Plateau), Cyprus, Georgia, Kirgizia, Iran, Mongolia, Russia (East Siberia, Far East and West Siberia), Syria, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan. Extralimital: India, Nepal, Pakistan (Aukema, 2023).

Figure 2. A – habitat of *Campylomma diversicorne*, B – habitat of *Camptotyliidea albovittata*, C – habitat of *Auchenocrepis alboscutellata*, D – habitat of *Camptozorus linnavuorii*.

***Megacoelum brevirostre* Reuter, 1879**

Material examined: Iran, South Khorasan province: Khorashad (32°75'126"N, 59°40'478"E. 1470m), 06.07.2022, 1 ♂.

This species was collected by light trap (Fig. 3-C, D).

Distribution in Iran: East Azerbaijan (Linnavuori, 2009), Fars (Linnavuori, 2009), Guilan (Linnavuori, 2007), Isfahan (Linnavuori, 2009), Kerman (Wagner, 1958; Hashemi Rad & Radjabi, 2002; Linnavuori, 2009), Khorasan (Linnavuori & Modarres Awal, 1999, Malvandi *et al.*, 2015 misidentification as *Adelphocoris insignis*), Khuzestan (Linnavuori, 2009), Markazi (Linnavuori, 2009), Sistan & Baluchestan (Reuter, 1904; Wagner, 1957), Yazd (Linnavuori, 2009), Zanjan (Linnavuori, 2007): cited references in Ghahari & Chérot (2014); Rafsanjan (Zeinadini *et al.*, 2015).

General distribution: Europe: Russia (South European Territory: Dagestan). Asia: Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Turkey, Cyprus, Iran, Iraq, Israel, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan (Aukema, 2023).

***Orthops (Montanorthops) pilosulus* Jakovlev, 1877**

Material examined: Iran, South Khorasan province: Bandedare (32°8'1049"N, 59°2'1985"E. 1760m), 15.07.2022, 1 ♀.

This species was collected by sweeping (Fig. 1-E).

Distribution in Iran: Guilan (Linnavuori, 2007), Kerman (Reuter, 1904 under the name *Lygus foreli* var *pilosulus*; Linnavuori, 2009), Khorasan (Linnavuori & Modarres Awal, 1999), Semnan (holotype from Shahrud cf. Kerzhner & Josifov, 1999; Linnavuori, 2007), Tehran (Linnavuori, 2007), Zanjan (Linnavuori, 2007), Northern Iran (no locality cited) (Jakovlev, 1877); cited references in Ghahari & Chérot (2014); Razavi Khorasan (Malvandi *et al.*, 2015), South Khorasan (Mohammadpour *et al.*, 2017).

General distribution: Asia: Kazakhstan, Iran, Kirgizia, Russia (East Siberia), Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan (Aukema, 2023).

***Orthops* sp.**

Material examined: Iran, South Khorasan province: Golefrize (32°68'842"N, 59°16'115"E. 1831m), 01.09.2022, 1 ♀.

This species was collected by light trap. This specimen remained at species level because it is female.

***Reuterista unicolor* Rosenzweig, 1997.**

Material examined: Iran, South Khorasan province: Piranj (33°03'585"N, 59°29'708"E. 1850m), 13.05.2022, 2 ♂♂.

This species was collected by light trap (Fig. 1-A).

Distribution in Iran: Razavi Khorasan (Linnavuori & Modarres Awal, 1999).

General distribution: Asia: China (Northwestern Territory), Iran, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan (Aukema, 2023).

Tribe Stenodemini China, 1943

***Trigonotylus caelestialium* (Kirkaldy, 1902)**

Material examined: Iran, South Khorasan province: Golefrize (32°68842'N, 59°16115'E. 1831m), 17.09.2022, 1 ♂.

This species was collected by light trap (Fig. 2-B).

Distribution in Iran: Ardabil (Linnavuori, 2007; Hosseini, 2013c), East Azerbaijan (Gharaat *et al.*, 2009; Linnavuori, 2009), Fars (Linnavuori, 2009), Golestan (Linnavuori, 2007), Guilan (Linnavuori, 2007; Hosseini, 2013c), Isfahan, Kermanshah (Linnavuori, 2009), Khorasan (Linnavuori & Modarres Awal, 1999), Khuzestan, Kordestan (Linnavuori, 2009), Kuhgiluyeh & Boyerahmad (Linnavuori, 2009), Mazandaran (Linnavuori, 2007), West Azerbaijan (Linnavuori, 2009; Gharaat *et al.*, 2009), Zanjan (Linnavuori, 2007); cited references in Ghahari & Chérot (2014).

General distribution: Europe: Albania, Austria, Belgium Bosnia, Hercegovina, Bulgaria, Byelorussia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Kazakhstan, Finland, France, Great Britain, Greece, Germany, Greece (Crete), Hungary, Italy, Liechtenstein, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Macedonia, Moldavia, Montenegro, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia (Central, North and South European Territories), Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine., North Africa: Azores. Asia: Armenia, Asian Kazakhstan, Azerbaijan, China (Central, Northeastern, Northern, Northwestern, Southwestern Territories), Georgia, Iran, Japan, Kirgizia, Korea, Mongolia, Russia (East Siberia, Far East and West Siberia), Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan. Extralimital: North America, Pakistan (Aukema, 2023).

Subfamily Phylinae Douglas & Scott, 1865

Tribe Phylini Douglas & Scott, 1865

***Compsidolon (Compsidolon) elegantulum* Reuter, 1899**

Material examined: Iran, South Khorasan province: Bandedare, 03.04.2022 (32°80876'N, 59°21553'E. 1834 m). 1 ♀. Piranj, 13.05.2022 (33°03585'N, 59°29708'E. 1850m) 2 ♀, 2♂.

This species was collected by light trap (Fig. 1-B).

Distribution in Iran: Fars (Linnavuori, 2010), Khorasan (Linnavuori & Modarres Awal, 1999), Tehran (Linnavuori, 2007).

General distribution: Asia: Asian Turkey, Iran, Iraq, Israel, Jordan, Syria (Aukema, 2023).

***Compsidolon (Compsidolon) nebulosum* (Reuter, 1878)**

Material examined: Iran, South Khorasan province: Afzalabad (33°13392'N, 59°21985'E. 1641m), 15.04.2022, 1 ♀, 21.07.2022 1 ♀, 3 ♂♂. Bandedare (32°80876'N, 59°21553'E. 1834 m), 23.04.2022, 5 ♀♀. Pasuj1 (33°01310' N, 59°29743'E. 1760m) 02.06.2022 7 ♀♀, Pasuj2 (33°01601'N, 59°29635'E. 1809m), 10.06.2022 2 ♀♀.

This species was collected on *Rosa* sp. By sweeping (Fig. 1-F).

Distribution in Iran: Alborz (Linnavuori, 2007), Fars (Linnavuori, 2010), Isfahan (Linnavuori, 2010), Kerman (Reuter, 1904 under the combination *Psallus nebulosus*) Kermanshah (Linnavuori, 2010), Khorasan (Wagner, 1957 under the combination *Psallus nebulosus*; Linnavuori & Modarres Awal, 1999), Kuhgiluyeh & Boyerahmad (Linnavuori, 2010), Semnan (Linnavuori, 2010), Sistan & Baluchestan (Wagner, 1957 under the

combination *Psallus nebulosus*; Kiritshenko, 1966), Tehran (Linnavuori, 2007), West Azerbaijan (Linnavuori, 2010), cited references in Ghahari & Chérot (2014).

General distribution: Asia: Armenia, Asian Kazakhstan, Azerbaijan, Iran, Kirgizia, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan (Aukema, 2023).

Subtribe Phylina Douglas & Scott, 1865

***Ectagela* sp.**

Material examined: Iran, South Khorasan province: Chahak (33°30239'N, 58°89859'E. 1380m), 31.07.2022 1 ♀.

This species was collected on *Pistachio vera* (Anacardiaceae) by sweeping. This specimen was not identified at species level (Fig. 3-A, B).

Tribe *Exaeretini* Puton, 1875

***Auchenocrepis alboscuteolata* Puton, 1874**

Material examined: Iran, South Khorasan province: Afzalabad (33°13392'N, 59°21985'E. 1641m), 21.07.2022, 4 ♂♂. Golefrize, 17.09.2022, 1 ♂. (32°68842'N, 59°16115'E. 1831m).

This species was collected by light trap (Fig. 2-C).

Distribution in Iran. Fars (Linnavuori, 2010), Hormozgan (Wagner, 1968; Linnavuori, 2004), Kerman (Wagner, 1958), Khorasan (Reuter, 1904 under the name *Auchenocrepis minutissima* var. *alboscuteolata*; Linnavuori & Modarres Awal, 1999), Khuzestan (Linnavuori, 2010), Sistan & Baluchestan (Wagner, 1957); cited references in Ghahari & Chérot (2014); Razavi Khorasan (Malvandi *et al.*, 2015).

General distribution: Europe: Italy (Pantelleria). North Africa: Algeria, Egypt, Libya, Morocco, Tunisia. Asia: Arab Emirates, Cyprus, Iran, Iraq, Israel, Jordan, Kuwait, Saudi Arabia, Syria, Yemen. Extralimital: tropical Africa (Niger, Sudan, W Sahara), Pakistan (Aukema, 2023).

***Camptozorus linnavouri* Kerzhner, 1996**

Material examined: Iran, South Khorasan province: Afzalabad (33°13392'N, 59°21985'E. 1641m), 21.07.2022, 1 ♂.

This species was collected by light trap (Fig. 2-D).

Distribution in Iran: Endemic Razavi Khorasan (Linnavuori and Modares Awal, 1999).

General distribution: Asia: Iran (Aukema, 2023).

Tribe *Nasocorini* Reuter, 1883

***Badezorus immaculatus* Linnavuori, 1997**

Material examined: Iran, South Khorasan province: Khorashad (32°75126'N, 59°40478'E. 1470m), 06.07.2022, 3 ♂♂.

This species was collected by light trap.

Distribution in Iran: Razavi Khorasan (Linnavuori, 1997; Linnavuori & Modarres Awal, 1999)

General distribution Asia: Asian Kazakhstan, Iran, Turkmenistan. (Aukema, 2023).

***Camptotylidea albovittata* (Reuter, 1903)**

Material examined: Iran, South Khorasan province: PIranj (33°03585'N, 59°29708'E. 1850m), 13.05.2022, 3 ♂♂. Pasuj2 (33°01601'N, 59°29635'E. 1809m), 10.06.2022, 2 ♀♀, 4 ♂♂. Khorashad (32°75126' N, 59°40478'E. 1470m), 06.07.2022, 14 ♀♀, 5 ♂♂. Afzalabad (33°13392'N, 59°21985'E. 1641m), 21.07.2022, 10 ♀♀, 14 ♂♂.

This species was collected by light trap (Fig. 2-A).

Distribution in Iran: Razavi Khorasan (Linnavuori and Modares Awal, 1999; Malvandi *et al.*, 2015).

General distribution: Asia: Asian Kazakhstan, Iran, Saudi Arabia, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan (Aukema, 2023).

***Camptotylidea sinaïtica* (Linnavuori, 1964)**

Material examined: Iran, South Khorasan province: Golefrize (32°68842'N, 59°16115'E. 1831m), 17.09.2022, 1 ♂.

This species was collected by light trap.

Distribution in Iran: Guilan (Linnavuori, 2007), Razavi Khorasan (Linnavuori, 1997).

General distribution: Asia: Iran, Sinai, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan (Aukema, 2023).

***Camptotylidea suturalis* (Reuter, 1903)**

Material examined: Iran, South Khorasan province: Afzalabad (33°13392'N, 59°16910'E. 1641m), 21.07.2022, 31 ♀♀, 20 ♂♂. PIranj (33°03585'N, 59°29708'E. 1850m), 13.05.2022, 1 ♀, 1 ♂. Khorashad (32°75126'N, 59°40478'E. 1470m), 06.07.2022, 5 ♀♀, 3 ♂♂.

This species was collected by light trap (Fig. 2-B).

Distribution in Iran: Fars (Linnavuori, 2010), Hormozgan (Linnavuori, 2004), Kerman (Wagner, 1958 under the original combination *Atomophora suturalis*), Khorasan (Linnavuori, & Modarres Awal, 1999), Sistan & Baluchestan (Wagner, 1957 under the original combination *Atomophora suturalis*; Linnavuori, 1986, Kerzhner & Josifov, 1999 under the name *C. alhagii*); cited references in Ghahari & Chérot (2014); Razavi Khorasan (Malvandi *et al.*, 2015).

General distribution: North Africa: Tunisia. Asia: Asian Kazakhstan, China (Northern, Northwestern Territories), Iran, Mongolia, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan (Aukema, 2023).

***Campylomma diversicorne* Reuter, 1878**

Material examined: Iran, South Khorasan province: Afzalabad (33°13392'N, 59°16910'E. 1641m), 21.07.2022, 2 ♀♀, 4 ♂♂. Golefrize (32°68842'N, 59°16115'E. 1831m), 01.09.2022, 3 ♀♀, 1 ♂. Khorashad (32°75126'N, 59°40478'E. 1470m), 06.07.2022, 5 ♀♀, 6 ♂♂.

This species was collected by light trap (Fig. 2-C).

Distribution in Iran: Ardabil (Linnavuori, 2007; Ghahari *et al.*, 2011), Bushehr (Linnavuori, 2010), East Azerbaijan (Khaghaninia *et al.*, 2010), Fars (Linnavuori, 2010; Zarei *et al.*, 2012), Golestan (Khormali, 2000; Ghahari & Ostovan, 2006; Ghahari *et al.*, 2011; Ghahari, 2013), Guilan (Linnavuori, 2007), Hamadan (Abd-

Rabou & Ghahari, 2006), Hormozgan (Wagner 1968; Linnavuori, 2004), Ilam (Linnavuori, 2010), Isfahan (Rakhshani *et al.*, 2010), Kerman (Reuter, 1904; Wagner, 1958; Mehrnejad & Linnavuori, 2012), Kermanshah (Linnavuori, 2010), Khorasan (Wagner, 1957; Abd-Rabou & Ghahari, 2006; Linnavuori & Modarres Awal, 1999; Havaskary *et al.*, 2010), Khuzestan (Farahbakhsh, 1961; Linnavuori, 2010), Kordestan (Linnavuori, 2010; Ebrahimi *et al.*, 2012), Kuhgiluyeh & Boyerahmad (Linnavuori, 2010), Markazi (Arkani *et al.*, 2011), Mazandaran (Ghahari & Ostovan, 2006; Ghahari *et al.*, 2011), Sistan & Baluchestan (Wagner, 1957), Tehran (Linnavuori, 2007), West Azerbaijan (Linnavuori, 2010), Zanjan (Linnavuori, 2007), cited references in Ghahari & Chérot (2014); Razavi Khorasan (Malvandi *et al.*, 2015).

General distribution: Europe: Bulgaria, European Turkey, Greece, Crete, Italy North Africa: Egypt Asia: Afghanistan, Arab Emirates, Armenia, Asian Kazakhstan, Asian Turkey, China (Northern, Northwestern and Southwestern Territories), Cyprus, Iran, Iraq, Israel, Kirgizia, Saudi, Arabia, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan. Extralimital: Pakistan (Aukema, 2023).

***Campylomma verbasci* (Meyer-Dür, 1843)**

Material examined: IRAN, South Khorasan province: Piranj (33°03585'N, 59°29708'E. 1850m), 13.05.2022, 2 ♀♀, 1 ♂. Pasuj2 (33°01601'N, 59°29635'E. 1809m), 10.06.2022, 2 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂. Khorashad (32°75126'N, 59°40478'E. 1470m), 06.07.2022, 1 ♀, 1 ♂. Afzalabad (33°13392'N, 59°16910'E. 1641m), 21.07.2022, 9 ♀♀, 12 ♂♂. Mazareerazg (32°80547'N, 59°26115'E. 1792m), 04.05.2022, 2 ♂♂. Bandeomarsah (32°83051'N, 59°18209'E. 1743m), 08.05.2022, 1 ♀, 2 ♂♂.

This species was collected by sweeping and light trap (Fig. 1-G).

Distribution in Iran: Ardabil (Linnavuori, 2007), East Azerbaijan (Abd-Rabou & Ghahari, 2006; Gharaat *et al.*, 2009), Fars (Linnavuori, 2010), Golestan (Ghahari & Ostovan, 2006; Ghahari *et al.*, 2011), Guilan (Linnavuori, 2007), Ilam (Linnavuori, 2010), Isfahan (Linnavuori, 2010), Kerman (Mehrnejad & Linnavuori, 2012; Ghahari *et al.*, 2011), Kermanshah (Abd-Rabou & Ghahari, 2006 under the junior synonym *C. nicolasi*; Linnavuori, 2010), Khorasan (Malkeshi *et al.*, 1998; Linnavuori & Modarres Awal, 1999; Havaskary *et al.*, 2010), Khuzestan (Modarres Awal, 1997c), Kordestan (Linnavuori 2010, Ebrahimi *et al.*, 2012), Lorestan (Linnavuori, 2010), Mazandaran (Heiss & Linnavuori, 2002), Tehran (Linnavuori, 2007), West Azerbaijan (Mostaan, 1993 under the spelling *campulomma* [sic] *verbasci*; Modarres Awal, 1997c; Pourhadji, 2001; Gharaat *et al.*, 2009; Linnavuori, 2010), Zanjan (Linnavuori, 2007), Northern Iran (no locality cited) (Jakovlev, 1877 under the generic name *Agallistest*), cited references in Ghahari & Chérot (2014).

General distribution: Europe: Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bosnia, Hercegovina, Bulgaria, Byelorussia, Crete, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, European, Kazakhstan, European, Turkey, Finland, France, Great Britain, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Kosovo, Latvia, Liechtenstein, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Moldavia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia (South European Territory), Serbia, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine. North Africa: Algeria, Canary Islands, Egypt, Libya, Morocco, Tunisia. Asia: Afghanistan, Armenia, Asian Kazakhstan, Asian Turkey, Azerbaijan, China (Northern and Northwestern Territory), Cyprus, Georgia, Iran, Israel, Jordan, Kirgizia, Lebanon, Saudi Arabia, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan. Extralimital: North America (introduced) (Aukema, 2023).

***Atomoscelis onusta* (Fieber, 1861)**

Material examined: Iran, South Khorasan province: Bujd (32°84054'N, 59°32416'E. 1550m), 31.03.2022, 5 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂. Piranj (33°03585'N, 59°29708'E. 1850m), 13.05.2022, 1 ♀, 1 ♂. Pasuj2 (33°01601'N, 59°29635'E. 1809m), 10.06.2022, 2 ♀♀, 5 ♂♂. Absharchardeh (32°80923'N, 59°24177'E. 1670m), 19.06.2022, 2 ♀♀. Khorashad (32°75126'N, 59°40478'E. 1470m), 06.07.2022, 15 ♀♀, 15 ♂♂. Afzalabad, 21.07.2022 (33°13392'N, 59°16910'E. 1641m) 16 ♀♀, 13 ♂♂.

This species was collected by light trap.

Distribution in Iran: Alborz, Ardabil (Linnavuori, 2007), Fars (Linnavuori, 2010), Golestan (Ghahari, 2013), Guilan (Linnavuori, 2007), Kerman (Wagner, 1958), Khorasan (Modarres Awal, 1997b; Linnavuori & Modarres Awal, 1999), Khuzestan (Linnavuori, 2010), Kordestan (Linnavuori, 2010), Tehran (Linnavuori 2007), West Azerbaijan (Linnavuori, 2010), Zanjan (Linnavuori, 2007); cited references in Ghahari & Chérot (2014).

General distribution: Europe: Austria, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, European Kazakhstan, European Turkey, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Macedonia, Moldavia, Netherlands, Romania, Russia (Central and South European Territories), Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Ukraine. North Africa: Algeria, Canary Islands, Morocco, Madeira, Tunisia. Asia: Azerbaijan, Afghanistan, Armenia, Asian Kazakhstan, Asian Turkey, China (Northern and Northwestern Territories), Georgia, Iran, Iraq, Israel, Jordan, Kirgizia Mongolia, Russia (East and West Siberia), Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, Yemen. Extralimital: North America (introduced), tropical Africa (W Sahara) (Aukema, 2023).

Figure 3. A, B – *Ectagela* sp., C, D – *Megacoelum brevirostre*, E, F – *Adelphocoris ticinensis*; Scale=1mm.

Conclusion

In total, 22 species were collected and identified from various host plants in South Khorasan province, with a focus on the city of Birjand and the vicinity, including 12 species belonging to Phyllinae (54.54%), 9 Mirinae species (40.9%) and 1 Deraeocorinae species (4.54%). This study reports three species including *Ectagela* sp., *Megacoelum brevirostre* and *Adelphocoris ticinensis* from South Khorasan province for the first time (Fig. 3).

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References

- Abd-Rabou, S., & Ghahari, H. (2006). Predators of whiteflies (Homoptera: Aleyrodidae) in Iran. *Trends in Entomology*, 5, 41-46.
- Alemansoor, H., & Ahmadi, A. A. (1993). Natural enemies of cotton whitefly, *Bemisia tabaci* (Gennadius) in Fars province. In *Proceeding of 11th Iranian Plant Protection Congress, Guilan University, Rasht*, 106 pp.
- Arkani, T., Hosseini, R., & Vafaei Shoushtari, R. (2011). Faunistic study of plant bugs (Miridae) and determination of dominant species in the agricultural farmlands and gardens of Arak and suburbs. *Journal of Entomological Research*, 3(2), 85-93. [in Persian, English summary].
- Aukema, B. (2023). Catalogue of Palaearctic Heteroptera. Naturalis Biodiversity Center. Retrieved from: <https://catpalhet.linnaeus.naturalis.nl> [Accessed on 20.06.2023].
- Cassis, G., & Schuh, R. (2012). Systematic, biodiversity, biogeography, and host associations of the Miridae (Insecta: Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Cimicomorpha). *The Annual Review of Entomology*, 57, 377-404.
- Ebrahimi, A., Hosseini, R., & Shoushtari, R. V. (2012). A faunal study of plant bugs (Hemiptera: Miridae) in Ghorveh and its counties (Kurdistan province, Iran). *Entomofauna*, 33(4), 25-40.
- Farahbakhsh, G. (1961). Order Heteroptera. In Farahbakhsh, G. (Ed.), Checklist of important insects and other enemies of plants and agricultural products in Iran. *Ministry of Agriculture, Department of Plant Protection, Tehran*, 24-28.
- Ghahari, H. (2013). A study on Miridae (Hemiptera: Heteroptera) from Golestan National Park, Northern Iran. *Linzer Biologische Beiträge*, 45(2), 191-198.
- Ghahari, H., & Ostovan, H. (2006). Predator arthropods' fauna of whiteflies (Homoptera: Aleyrodidae) in Mazandaran and Golestan Provinces and their feeding efficiency. *Journal of Agriculture and Natural Resources Science*, 12(6), 171-180. [in Persian, English Summary].
- Ghahari, H., Ostovan, H., Kamali, K., & Tabari, M. (2008a). Arthropod predators of rice fields in central parts of Mazandaran. *Journal of Agricultural Science (Islamic Azad University)*, 14 (1), 63-74. [in Persian, English summary].
- Ghahari, H., Chérot, F., Ostovan, H., & Sakenin, H. (2008b). Heteroptera from rice fields and surrounding grasslands of northern Iran (Insecta), with special emphasis on predator species. *Journal of Entomological Research Society*, 10(1), 13-25.
- Ghahari, H., Ostovan, H., & Tabari, M. (2009). Species diversity and population fluctuation of Heteroptera predators in rice fields of Mazandaran province, northern Iran. *Journal of Plant Protection*, 1 (1), 27-41. [in Persian, English Summary].

- Ghahari, H., Chérot, F., Moulet, P., Carpintero, D.L., Linnavuori, R.E., Sakenin, H., & Ostovan, H. (2011). Heteroptera (Insecta) fauna of Iranian cotton fields and surrounding grasslands. *Entomologie faunistique*, 64, 3-13.
- Ghahari, H., & Chérot, F. (2014). An annotated catalog of the Iranian Miridae (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Cimicomorpha). *Zootaxa*, 3845(1), 1-101.
- Gharaat, M. A., Hassanzadeh, M., Safaralizadeh, M. H., & Fallahzadeh, M. (2009). Notes on the true bug (Heteroptera) fauna of Azerbaijan province, Iran. *Turkish Journal of Zoology* 33, 421-431.
- Hassazadeh, M., Farshbaf Pour-Abad, R., & Shayesteh, N. (2009a). An investigation on some Heteroptera in Marand region (Iran). *Munis Entomology & Zoology*, 4(1), 19-24.
- Hassazadeh, M., Farshbaf Pour-Abad, R., Gharaat, M. A., & Beykpor, A. R. (2009b). A study of the Heteroptera fauna of Shend Abad Region and environ (Iran). *Munis Entomology & Zoology*, 4(2), 527-530.
- Hashemi Rad, H., & Radjabi, A. (2002). Study on the biology of the new pistachio bugs (Hemi.: Miridae) in Kerman province. In *Proceedings of 15th Iranian Plant Protection Congress, Razi University, Kermanshah*, 107 pp.
- Havaskary, M., Hossein Pour, F., & Modarres Awal, M. (2010). Cimicomorpha and Pentatomomorpha (Heteroptera) of alfalfa from Mashhad and vicinity, NE Iran. *Munis Entomology & Zoology*, 5, 253- 261.
- Havaskary, M., Farshbaf Pour-Abad, R., Kazemi, M. H., Refeii, A., & Havaskary, S. (2012). An investigation to the fauna of Cimicomorpha (Heteroptera) from Parsabad-e-Moghan and vicinity, New Iran. *Munis Entomology & Zoology*, 7, 1101-1105.
- Heiss, E., & Linnavuori, R. E. (2000). Beitrage zur Kenntnis der Wanzenfauna Irans, II. *Carinthia*, 192, 615-632.
- Hoberlandt, L. (1955). Hemiptera—Heteroptera from Iran, I. *Acta Entomologica Musei Nationalis Pragae*, 29(1954), 121-148.
- Hosseini, R. (2013a). On the genus *Pilophorus* Hahn (Hemiptera: Miridae) in Guilan province and adjacent areas. *Entomofauna* 34, 105-116.
- Hosseini, R. (2013b). On the tribe Dicyphini (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Miridae: Bryocorinae) in Guilan province and adjacent area (Iran). *Entomofauna*, 34, 157-158.
- Hosseini, R. (2013c). On the tribe Stenodemini (Hemiptera: Miridae: Mirinae) in Guilan province and adjacent areas (Iran). *Entomofauna*, 34, 377-396.
- Hosseini, R. (2014a). A study on the genus *Orthops* Fieber (Hemiptera: Miridae: Mirinae) in Iran. *Arthropods*, 1, 57-69.
- Hosseini, R. (2014b). On the genus *Adelphocoris* (Hemiptera: Miridae) in Guilan province (Iran) and its adjacent areas. *Entomofauna*, 35, 413-421.
- Hosseini, R. (2016). A review on the genus *Brachycoleus* (Hemiptera, Miridae) with identification key to the species found in Iran. *Vestnik zoologii*, 50(2), 105-110.
- Hosseini, R. (2017). A new species of *Isometopus* from Iran (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Miridae: Isometopinae). *Acta Entomologica Musei Nationalis Pragae*, 57(1), 23-34.
- Hosseini, R., & Linnavuori, R. E. (2000). A faunal study on the mirids of Guilan province (Het.: Miridae, Orthotylinae). In *Proceeding of the 14th Iranian Plant Protection Congress* (p. 357). Isfahan University of Technology, Iran.
- Hosseini, R., Linnavuori, R. E., Sahragard A., & Hajizadeh, J. (2000). Taxonomic study on the Miridae (Heteroptera) of Guilan province (sub family: Orthotylinae). In *Proceeding of the 14th Iranian plant protection congress 2000 Sep.* 5-8.
- Hosseini, R., & Shamsi, M. (2014). A new species of the genus *Ectagela* Schmidt from Iran (Hemiptera, Heteroptera, Miridae, Phylinae). *Zootaxa*, 3802, 389- 394.
- Hosseini, R., & Mohammadi, S. (2018). A new species of the genus *Phytocoris* (Hemiptera: Miridae) from western Iran. *Zootaxa*, 4446(4), 567-574.
- Hosseini, R., & Mohammadi, S. (2019a). A new species of the genus *Phytocoris* (Hemiptera: Miridae), with an identification key to *amygdali*-group species of the subgenus *Compocorocoris* found in Iran. *Zootaxa*, 4563(2), 354-360.

- Hosseini, R., & Mohammadi, S. (2019b). A new species of the genus *Brachycoleus* (Hemiptera: Miridae), with a revised identification key to the species found in Iran. *Acta Entomologica Musei Nationalis Pragae*, 59(1), 63-69.
- Jakovlev, V.E. (1877). True bugs (Hemiptera Heteroptera) of northern Iran. *Trudy Russkago Entomologicheskago Obshchestva*, 10, 67-98. [in Russian].
- Karimian, Z., & Khormali, S. (2006). Identification the cotton damaging bugs and determining the abundance of major species in different microclimate of Golestan province. In *Proceeding of the 17th Iranian Congress; 2-5 Sept. 2006, Karaj, Iran*. Tehran University Press, 83 pp.
- Kerzhner, I.M., & Josifov, M. (1999). Miridae. In: Aukema, B. & Rieger, C. (Eds.), *Catalogue of the Heteroptera of the Palaearctic region*. Cimicomorpha II. The Netherlands Entomological Society, Amsterdam, 577 pp.
- Khaghaninia, S., Farshbaf Pour-Abad, R., Askari, O., & Fent, M. (2010). An introduction to true bugs fauna of Gunber valley including two new records for Iranian fauna (Hemiptera: Heteroptera). *Munis Entomology & Zoology*, 5(2), 354-360.
- Khanjani, M., & Kalafchi, M. (2000). Recognition of seed crop alfalfa pests and study on the biology of dominant injurious species in Hamadan. *Proceedings of 14th Iranian Plant Protection Congress, Isfahan University of Technology, Isfahan*, 24 pp.
- Khormali, S. (2000). Mirid bugs damaging cotton in Gonbad region and investigation on dominant species. *Proceedings of 14th Iranian Plant Protection Congress, Isfahan University of Technology, Isfahan*, 43 pp.
- Kiritshenko, A. N. (1966). Hemiptera Heteroptera collected by D.M. Steinberg in Iran in 1955. *Revue d'Entomologie de l'URSS*, 45(4), 798-803.
- Konstantinov, F. V. (1999). Revision of the genus *Camptotylidea* (Heteroptera: Miridae). *Zoosystematica Rossica*, 8, 89-119.
- Lashkari, M., & Hosseini, R. (2012). A revised identification key to the *Lygus* species in Iran (Hemiptera: Miridae). *Entomofauna*, 33, 81-92.
- Linnavuori, R. E. (1986). Heteroptera of Saudi Arabia. *Fauna of Saudi Arabia*, 5, 31-197.
- Linnavuori, R. E. (1993). Hemiptera of Iraq. III. Heteroptera, Miridae (Phylinae). - *Entomol. Fennica*, 4, 253-271.
- Linnavuori, R. E. (1997). Taxonomic studies on the Miridae (Heteroptera) of Africa and the Middle East. *Acta Universitatis Carolinae Biologica*, 40 (1996), 321-350.
- Linnavuori, R. E. (2004). Heteroptera of the Hormozgan province in Iran II. Nepomorpha, Gerromorpha, Leptopodomorpha, Cimicomorpha (Nabidae, Anthocoridae, Miridae). *Acta Universitatis Carolinae Biologica*, 48, 85-98.
- Linnavuori R. E. (2006). Studies on the Miridae (Heteroptera) of Gilan and the adjacent provinces in northern Iran. I. Description of new species. *Acta Universitatis Carolinae Biologica*, 49, 219-243.
- Linnavuori, R. E. (2007). Studies on the Miridae (Heteroptera) of Gilan and the adjacent provinces in northern Iran. II. List of species. *Acta Entomologica Musei Nationalis Pragae*, 47, 17-56.
- Linnavuori, R. E. (2009). Studies on the Nepomorpha, Gerromorpha, Leptopodomorpha and Miridae excluding Phylini (Hemiptera: Heteroptera) of Khuzestan and the adjacent provinces of Iran. *Acta Entomologica Musei Nationalis Pragae*, 49(1), 1-32.
- Linnavuori, R. E. (2010). Studies on the Miridae (Phylinae, addenda to Deraeocorinae and Orthotylinae) of Khuzestan and the adjacent provinces of Iran (Hemiptera: Heteroptera). *Acta Entomologica Musei Nationalis Pragae*, 50(2), 369-414.
- Linnavuori, R. E., & Hosseini, R. (1998). New species of the miridae (Heteroptera) from Iran. *Acta Universitatis Carolinae, Biologica*, 42, 3-15.
- Linnavuori, R. E., & Hosseini, R. (1999). On the genus *Dicyphus* (Heteroptera, Miridae, Dicyphinae) in Iran. *Acta Universitatis Carolinae, Biologica*, 43, 155-162.
- Linnavuori, R. E., & Hosseini, R. (2000). On the *Polymerus* subgenus *Poeciloscytus* Fieber (Heteroptera, Miridae, Mirinae) in Iran. *Acta Universitatis Carolinae, Biologica*, 44, 189-194.

- Linnavuori, R. E., & Modarres, M. (1998). Studies on the Heteroptera of the Khorasan province in N. E. Iran. I. Nepomorpha, Gerromorpha, Leptopodomorpha, Cimicomorpha (Nabidae, Anthocoridae), and Pentatomorpha (Coreoidea). *Entomol. Fennica*, 9, 237-241.
- Linnavuori, R. E., & Modarres, M. (1999). Studies on the Heteroptera of the Khorasan province in N. E. Iran. II. Cimicomorpha: Miridae. *Entomologica Fennica*, 10, 215-231.
- Magnien, P., & Matocq, A. (2008). A new species of *Cyllecoris* Hahn, 1834 from Iran (Heteroptera, Miridae, Orthotylinae). *Nouvelle Revue d'Entomologie*, 25(3), 235-240.
- Malvandi, A., Hosseini, R., & Hajizadeh, J. (2015). A preliminary study on the Miridae (Hemiptera) fauna in Sabzevar and its counties (Razavi Khorasan, Iran). *Acta Entomologica Serbica*, 20(1), 1-11.
- Malkeshi, H., Rezvani, A., & Talebi, A. A. (1998). Identification of important natural enemies of pome fruit trees aphids in Bojnord. In *Proceedings of 13th Iranian Plant Protection Congress, Campus of Agriculture and Natural Resources, University of Tehran, Karaj*, 163 pp.
- Mehrnejad, M. R., & Linnavuori, R. E. (2012). Four major mirid bugs of pistachio trees in Iran. *Applied Entomology and Phytopathology*, 79(2), 277-279.
- Menard, K. L., Schuh, R. T., & Woolley, J. B. (2013). Total-evidence phylogenetic analysis and reclassification of the Phylinae (Insecta: Heteroptera: Miridae), with the recognition of new tribes and subtribes and a redefinition of Phylini. *Cladistics*, 1-37.
- Mirab-balou, M., & Radjabi, R. (2013). *Lygus rugulipennis* Poppius (Hemiptera: Miridae): A key pest on alfalfa (*Medicago sativa* L.) in west of Iran, and checklist of the insect pests. *Persian Gulf Crop Protection*, 2(1), 57-66.
- Miyamoto, S. (1963). Heteropterous Insects from Iran and Afghanistan. In: Ueno, M. (Ed.), Results of the Kyoto University Scientific Expedition to the Karakorum and Hindukush, 1955. Vol. IV. *Insect fauna of Afghanistan and Hindukush. Kyoto University, Kyoto*, 89-92.
- Modarres Awal, M. (1997a). Determination of some fauna of Cimicomorpha and Pentatomorpha (Het.) in Tabriz area. *Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 7: 43-56.
- Modarres Awal, M. (1997b). Studies on some of Miridae, Reduviidae and Tingidae fauna in north of Khorasan province. *Journal of Agricultural Science & Technology University of Mashad*, 1: 89-96. [in Persian with English summary].
- Modarres Awal, M. (1997c). Family Miridae. In: Modarres Awal, M. (Ed.), List of agricultural pests and their natural enemies in Iran. *Ferdowsi University Press, Mashhad*, 73-75.
- Mohammadpour, M., Hosseini, M., Matocq, A., & Fekrat, L. (2017). Heteroptera fauna in alfalfa fields of Ghaen and vicinity, South Khorasan province, with a new record for Iran. *Iranian Journal of Animal Biosystematics*, 13(1), 9-21.
- Mohammadi, S., Hosseini, R., & Hajizadeh, J. (2018a). First record of *Brachycoleus thoracicus* Puton, 1892 (Hemiptera, Miridae) from Iran. *Acta Entomologica Serbica*, 23(1), 19-23.
- Mohammadi, S., Hosseini, R., & Hajizadeh, J. (2018b). First report of *Camponotidea saundersi* (Hemiptera, Heteroptera, Miridae) from Iran. *Journal of Entomological Society of Iran*, 38(2), 247-251.
- Mostaan, M. (1993). Natural enemies of European red mite in apple orchards of Oromieh region, West Azerbaijan, Iran. In *Proceedings of 11th Iranian Plant Protection Congress, University of Guilan, Rasht*, 199 pp.
- Namyatova, A. A., & Cassis, G. (2016). Systematic revision and phylogeny of the plant bug tribe Monaloniini (Insecta: Heteroptera: Miridae: Bryocorinae) of the world. *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society*, 176(1), 36-136.
- Nikdel, M., Dordaei, A. A., & Matocq, A. (2011). Faunistic study on Hemiptera in Arasbaran area (East Azerbaijan province, Iran). *Munis Entomology & Zoology*, 6(1), 389-395.
- Pourhadji, A. (2001). Biology of *Campylomma verbasci* (Meyer - Dür) (Hem.: Miridae) and its injury in apple orchards of West Azarbaijan. *Journal of Entomological Society of Iran*, 20(2), 47-55.
- Protić, Lj. 1998. Catalogue of the Heteroptera fauna of Yugoslav countries. Part one. - *Natural History Museum, Belgrade. Special issue 38*, 1-215.

- Rakhshani, H., Ebadi R., Hatami, B., Rakhshani, E., & Gharali, B. (2010). A survey of alfalfa aphids and their natural enemies in Isfahan, Iran, and the effect of alfalfa strip-harvesting on their populations. *Journal of Entomological Society of Iran*, 30(1), 13-28.
- Razmjoo, M., Mortezae Nejjad, F., Jalali Zand, A. & Jafarpour, M. (2011). Study on Heteroptera in biotope of alfalfa fields in Isfahan province. *International Conference on Life Science and Technology IPCBEE Vol.3 (2011)*, IACSIT Press, Singapore, 150-152.
- Reuter, O. M. (1904). Capsidae persicae D: N. A. Zarudny collectae enumeratae novaeque species descriptae. *Ezhagodnik Zoologicheskogo Nuseya Imperatorskoi Akademii Nauk*, 9, 5-16.
- Sadullaevich, B. A., & Mirganieva, M. M. (2022). Fauna and Plant Nutrition of Bed-bugs Belonging to the Family of Mirid (Miridae) Found in Cotton, Alfalfa, Vegetable Agroecosystems and Natural Ecosystems of the Amudarya and Khodjayli Districts of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. *European Journal of Agricultural and Rural Education*, 3(2), 69-74.
- Sadaghian, B., Dordaei, A. A., & Nikdel, M. (2004). An investigation on some Heteroptera in Arasbaran forests. In *Proceedings of 16th Iranian Plant Protection Congress, Tabriz University*, 128 pp.
- Shamsi, M., Hosseini, R., & Shirvani, A. (2014). Checklist of the subfamilies Mirinae and Orthotylinae (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Miridae) in western parts of Kerman Province, Iran, 3(1), 48.
- The General Bureau for Textbooks Printing and Distribution (2023). <http://chap.sch.ir/books/10227> (Geography of South Khorasan province). Retrieved from: <http://chap.sch.ir/books/10227> [Accessed on: 01.06. 2023].
- Wagner, E. (1957). Heteropteren aus Iran 1954 II. Teil Hemiptera-Heteroptera (Fam. Miridae). Ergebnisse der Entomologischen Reisen Willi Richter, Stuttgart, in Iran 1954 und 1956-Nr. 9. *Jahreshefte des Vereins für Vaterländische Naturkunde in Württemberg*, 122, 74-103.
- Wagner, E. (1958). Heteropteren aus Iran 1956, II. Hemiptera-Heteroptera (Familie Miridae). Ergebnisse der Entomologischen Reisen Willi Richter, Stuttgart, im Iran 1954 und 1956-Nr. 18. *Stuttgarter Beiträge zur Naturkunde*, 12, 1-13.
- Wagner, E. (1961). Beitrag zur Heteropteren-Fauna von Iran. Ergebnisse der Österreichischen Iran-Expeditionen 1949/1950 und 1956. *Anzeiger der Österreichische Akademie für Wissenschaften, Mathematisch-Naturwissenschaftliche Klasse*, 10, 156-165.
- Wagner, E. (1968). Contribution à la fauna de l'Iran. 7. Hemipteres: Heteropteres (pro parte). *Annales de la Société Entomologique de France, N. S.*, 4, 437-453.
- Yarmand, H., Sadeghi, S. E., Asgari, H., Mehrabi, A. & Matocq, A. (2004). Diversity of some Miridae (Heteroptera) species associated with forests and rangelands of Iran. In *Proceedings of 16th Iranian Plant Protection Congress, University of Tabriz, Tabriz*, 154 pp
- Zeinadini, N., Awal, M. M., & Karimi, J. (2015). Faunistic and molecular surveys on the pistachio Hemiptera of Rafsanjan region and vicinity, South East Iran. *Journal of the Entomological Research Society*, 17(2), 23-31.
- Zamani, M., & Hosseini, R. (2018). First report of *Grypocoris fieberi* Douglas & Scott, 1868 (Hem.: Miridae: Mirinae) for the Iranian fauna. *Plant Pest Research*, 8(2), 83-87.
- Zamani, M., & Hosseini, R. (2019). Two new species of the genus *Phytocoris* (Hemiptera: Miridae), with a revised identification key to species of the subgenus *Compsocorocoris* found in Iran. *Zootaxa*, 4648(1), 130-140.
- Zamani M., & Hosseini R. (2020). An illustrated taxonomic key to genera of Mirinae (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Miridae) with three new records from Iran. *Russian Entomological Journal*, 29(1), 20-32.
- Zamani, M., & Hosseini, R., (2022). A phylogenetic study of the relationships within Mirinae subfamily (Insecta: Heteroptera: Miridae) based on specimens from Northern Iran: Insight into analyses of genera complexes. *Zootaxa*, 5200(2), 101-127.
- Zarei, A., Dousti, A., & Fallahzadeh, M. (2012). Fauna survey of family Miridae (Hemiptera: Heteroptera) in Darab-Fars. In *Proceedings of 20th Iranian Plant Protection Congress, University of Shiraz, Shiraz*, 99 pp.

ФАУНИСТИЧКА ИСТРАЖИВАЊА СТЕНИЦА (HEMIPTERA: HETEROPTERA: MIRIDAE) У ЦЕНТРАЛНОМ ДЕЛУ ПРОВИНЦИЈЕ ЈУЖНИ ХОРАСАН, ИРАН

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Извод

Ово истраживање је спроведено 2022. године у централном делу провинције Јужни Хорасан, Иран. Прикупљене су 22 врсте стеница (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Miridae) из 17 родова и 3 потфамилије, укључујући Deraeocorinae (1 род и 1 врста), Mirinae (8 родова и 9 врста) и Phyllinae (8 родова) сакупљених на 12 различитих врста биљака домаћина. У овом раду су по први пут регистроване три врсте из провинције Јужни Хорасан, то су: *Ectagela* sp., *Megacoelum brevirostre* и *Adelphocoris ticinensis*. Сви примерци су сачувани у колекцији инсеката Природњачког музеја Универзитета Гилан.

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